

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Supply chains and COVID-19: impact on Jordan’s, countermeasures and post-COVID-19 era

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to assess existing information on the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on Jordan's supply chain and countermeasures adopted by businesses to mitigate supply chain interruptions. Many effects have been felt in the supply chain industry. The study will explain how travel restrictions have reduced international trade which has also affected Jordan’s supply chain. Global business leaders may use information from this study in making necessary decisions relating to trade activities in the country. It will assess Impacts of COVID 19 in the supply chain Industry in Jordan particularly the impacts of supply chain on demand, on logistics, manufacturing, and finally on people. A series of economic implications and research options are provided based on these results.

Keywords: Global supply chain; manufacturing; demand; supply; logistics

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1. Introduction

Corona virus which is scientifically known as COVID 19 is one of the major deadly viruses ever experienced and evidenced in the world (Peeri et al., 2020). The virus outbreak became a major issue to almost 80% of global countries (WHO, 2020). Jordan imposed major travel restrictions and cessation of movement in many regions. This was to help reduce the spread of the virus to other citizens as the disease caused many deaths among citizens (Baldwin & Di Mauro, 2020). The country also experienced rapid infection rates of the disease within its borders. Without observing and implementing health guidelines to help reduce the spread of the virus, Jordan would have lost many people to the disease (Alzoubi et al., 2020). However, there were many preventive measures which were put in place to help reduce the spread of the virus in the region.

The pandemic's immediate impact on businesses is already severe, and the medium-to long-term implications are projected to be substantially worse (Haren and Simchi-Levi,

2020). COVID-19, according to a recent study, has produced instability in 94% of Fortune 1,000 companies (Fortune, 2020). According to a Dun & Bradstreet (2020) survey, 51,000 global corporations have one or more direct suppliers in Wuhan, and at least 5 million organizations have one or more tier-two suppliers in the Wuhan area, which is where COVID-19 originated. Additionally, a recent survey found that almost 938 Fortune 1,000 companies have tier-one or tier-two suppliers in the Wuhan area (Dun and Bradstreet, 2020).

The significant economic reforms enacted by Jordan throughout the previous two decades and various structural adjustment programs have resulted in nearly doubling the average Gross Domestic Product (GDP) during the 2010-2018 period and posted a 1.9 percent increase for 2018 (Forster et al., 2020). The transport industry which is one of the essential components of the infrastructure has a substantial influence on the economic growth of the nation and accounted for roughly 8.4 percent of Jordan’s GDP in 2017. The announced plans to create a 1,000-kilometer railway network in Jordan which would